

Firelogue

Fire Up the Dialogue

D1.4 KNOWLEDGE BASE FOR DIALOGUE WORKSHOPS- INTERIM REPORT

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Acronym: **Firelogue**

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Responsible Author	Eva Preinfalk, John Handmer, Thomas Schinko		
Contributions from	Mariza Kaskara, Hugo Miguel Silva, Diana Viegas, Jose Maria Costa Saura		

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Executive Summary

With its lack of controllability, predictability, certainty and security, wildfire is a complex risk. It presents challenges for risk governance and raises the need to account for plurality across and within societies, as well as issues of inclusivity, differential distribution of risk, equity and justice. As WFRM constitutes a multi-level and complex matter, a broad and heterogenous range of individuals have a stake, creating the potential for conflicting interests and also synergies with respect to aspects of sustainability, fairness, economic interests, or biodiversity.

Through a systems approach, the Firelogue project supports and coordinates the identification of synergies and trade-offs of different wildfire risk management (WFRM) approaches and technologies throughout the different disaster management phases.

The project supports Innovation Actions (IAs) in coordinating and integrating their outputs to generate cross-sectoral WFRM recommendations into a roadmap for 2030 and beyond. To achieve this, integrated dialogue formats play an important role, identifying conflicts and synergies and effective measures to overcome conflicts. Firelogue working group (WG) workshops will enable and facilitate this exchange, supporting the aim to coordinate and support the integration of IA findings across stakeholders and fire management.

The aim of this document (Deliverable 1.4 (D1.4)) is to serve as a resource for wildfire related knowledge both for the WFRM community and to feed into and support working group (WG) discussions. Thus, it contributes towards Firelogue's cooperation objective 5 - aiming to organize dialogues within and across WGs; and also supports strategic and policy objectives 1 and 2 by contributing to the identification of synergies and conflicts in WFRM, as well as potential measures to overcome real and perceived injustices. This interim version of D1.4 builds on evidence from existing wildfire risk and WFRM research and thematic strand (TS) expertise. It constitutes a living document, continuously updated by WG discussions and knowledge from the IAs and FireEUrisk, as well as broader WFRM related research activities.

Figure ES 1 Wildfire risk as an intersection of hazard, exposure and vulnerability. Illustration based on IPCC (2022b) with extensions.

Wildfire risk emerges at the intersection of hazard, exposure and vulnerability, and can be considered a **socio-natural hazard**, as it is determined both by natural and anthropogenic factors. Despite a noticeable reduction in the number and size of fires since the 1980s in the most affected countries, the length of the fire season has increased as a result of climate change. In addition to climate and weather, wildfire hazard has a socioeconomic dimension. Rural depopulation, farmland abandonment and concomitant afforestation has led to a significant increase in fuel, increasing the fire hazard and in turn shifting fire regimes in Southern Europe. It is due to this interconnectedness and complexity, that there is no single solution to managing the hazard of wildfires.

In Europe, apart from climate change a major driver of wildfire hazard is the development of unmanaged fuel-intensive landscapes on abandoned farmland. Exposure of lives, assets and economic activity is increasing as expanding rural-urban interfaces and poor land planning ignore wildfire risk. The third component of wildfire risk, vulnerability, is situation and context dependent, indicating a complex interdependency between the severity of a wildfire event and the impacts on the affected community.

Current European approaches to wildfire risk management are challenged by both this complexity and an increase in the magnitude and severity of fires. More effective and integrated solutions are called for. Firelogue aims to connect the European WFRM community to co-create holistic and innovative WFRM strategies, that are effective in reducing wildfire risk and perceived as just by affected communities.

By building on existing wildfire risk and WFRM research, as well as TS expertise, this interim version of D1.4 starts to set out a knowledge base for dialogue WG workshops. It is a living document expected to be regularly updated with insights from WG discussions and IA and FireEUrisk innovations.

This document serves as a source for framing WG discussions and identifying WG topics, contributing towards the overarching aim of Firelogue, which is to create a network for discussion of future WFRM in Europe and to connect the broader WFRM community. For a horizontal integration of workshop discussions, this deliverable includes Factsheets structured against the background of the four thematic strands (TS): i) socioeconomic, ii) climate change mitigation and adaptation, iii) technology, and iv) earth observation.

During early 2023, close interaction between the Socioeconomic and Climate Change TS and WGs will inform the identification of discussion topics and relevant policy aspects in WFRM. This will feed back into and refine the TS factsheets, to serve as a basis for thematic input into cross-WG exchange. This procedure is then repeated towards the end of the second project year for the second workshop cycle, focusing on the thematic strands on Technology and Earth Observation. Ongoing work in WP1 will contribute to the knowledge collection conducted in this task. Insights and lessons learned from past wildfire events are also being analyzed through a review of existing peer-reviewed and grey literature in Task 1.2. And innovations from IAs and FireEUrisk are collected by Task 1.3. Thus, we aim to establish a comprehensive collection of novel and past WFRM practices, serving as an extensive knowledge base for the informed design of effective and inclusive future wildfire management across Europe.

1. Introduction

Firelogue supports and coordinates the identification of synergies and trade-offs of different wildfire risk management (WFRM) approaches and technologies throughout the different disaster risk management phases. Thereby, the project strives to adopt a systems perspective to WFRM (Handmer et al., 2020), acknowledging the interdependency of associated social and economic systems nested in the natural environment. Yet, it is due to this interconnectedness and complexity, that there is no single solution to managing wildfire risk, making wildfires wicked governance problems (Essen et al., 2022; Wunder et al., 2021). With WFRM constituting a multi-level and complex matter, a broad and heterogenous range of individuals have a stake in WFRM, creating the potential for conflicting interests and also synergies with respect to aspects of sustainability, fairness, economic interests, or biodiversity.

This project supports Innovation Actions (IAs) in coordinating and integrating their outputs and connecting actors to generate cross-sectoral WFRM recommendations into a roadmap for 2030 and beyond. To achieve this, integrated dialogue formats play an important role, identifying conflicts and synergies as well as effective measures to overcome conflicts. Firelogue working group (WG) workshops will enable and facilitate this exchange. Supporting the aim to coordinate and support the integration of IA findings across stakeholders and fire risk management, this interim version of Deliverable 1.4 (D1.4) synthesises recent knowledge on the determinants of wildfire risk and integrated management practices in the context of Europe. It is based on desk research and the knowledge gathered by Firelogue, with the aim of informing WG exchange. For a horizontal integration of workshop discussions, this deliverable includes Factsheets structured against the background of the four thematic strands (TS): i) socioeconomic, ii) climate change mitigation and adaptation, iii) technology, and iv) earth observation. This deliverable serves as a source document for framing WG discussions and identifying overarching WG topics, contributing towards the overarching aim of Firelogue, which is to create a network for discussion of future WFRM in Europe and to connect the broader WFRM community.

This interim version of D1.4 builds on evidence from existing research on wildfire risk and WFRM and TS expertise and constitutes a living document, continuously updated by WG discussions and knowledge from the IAs and FireEUrisk, as well as broader WFRM related research activities. The overall aim of this document is to serve as a comprehensive resource for wildfire related knowledge, both for the WFRM community and also to feed into and support WG discussions. In particular, we focus on aspects relevant in the European context as the overall project's aim is to identify and understand the drivers and resulting dynamics of European wildfire risk. The purpose of this document is to establish a common understanding of European wildfire risk, while also highlighting the diversity in the manifestation of wildfire risk, related impacts and adequate management options across different European contexts. This deliverable serves as a background document for integrating the solutions by our European partner projects, as they become available throughout the next years of the project. Thus, we contribute towards Firelogue's cooperation objective 5, aiming to organize dialogues within and across sectoral WGs along horizontal topics collecting relevant topics and supports strategic and policy objectives 1 and 2 by contributing to the identification of synergies and conflicts of WFRM, as well as potential measures to overcome real and perceived injustices building on the just transition (JT) framework.

The structure of this deliverable is as follows: the Section 2 discusses the integrated systems thinking approach adopted by this project and conceptualises it in the context of WFRM. Thereby, we dissect existing research on wildfire risk factors and management phases, focusing on the European context. Also, we embed WFRM in the respective socio-economic context, acknowledging the complex socio-ecological and economic interconnectedness of wildfire risk and associated management strategies. Building on this knowledge, section 3 introduces the TS, raising relevant topics and points for discussion across WGs. Section 4 concludes and discusses further steps.

2. Building on an Integrated Systems Thinking approach

Contrasting the notion of simple risk that assumes a complete and undisputed understanding of the causes and effects or risk, with optimal and universal solutions available (Essen et al., 2022), climate risks are challenging this notion, calling for a more complex understanding of risk (Rittel & Webber, 1973). As one of a number of *wicked problems*, forest fires (Essen et al., 2022; Wunder et al., 2021), are challenging risk governance, bringing issues of equity to the table and the need to account for the pluralism among and across societies (Rittel & Webber, 1973). Shifting away from controllability, predictability, certainty and security (Essen et al., 2022), complex risk requires a profound understanding about the underlying definition of risk and the decisions made and their consequences on affected communities (van Asselt & Renn, 2011). This raises questions of inclusivity, differential distribution of risk, equity and justice (Klinke & Renn, 2012).

The systemic and cross-sectoral dimension of WFRM has long been acknowledged by the research community for a long time and has become an integral part of risk management (Badia et al., 2002; Costa et al., 2011; Gill, 2005; Moreira et al., 2011; Rego et al., 2007). In line with recent scientific consensus (Bacciu et al., 2022; Essen et al., 2022; McWethy et al., 2019; Wunder et al., 2021), Firelogue adopts a more complex definition of wildfire risk, recognising it as a wicked governance problem. Acknowledging wildfires as a systemic risk, defined by the interconnection, interaction and dynamics of multiple risks and cascading effects (Li et al., 2021), this project aims to connect the European WFRM community to identify related conflicting and synergistic interests and co-create holistic WFRM strategies. Thereby, WGs serve as a facilitating space and discussion platform of IA innovations and associated consequences on the components of climate risk and the integration of WFRM knowledge into different wildfire risk management phases. A careful embedding into the relevant socioeconomic context and the accommodation of different notions of justice serve as the basis for structuring WG exchange.

2.1 Dissecting wildfire risk in a European context

We adopt the (IPCC, 2022b, p.43) WG II definition of risk, describing it “as the potential for adverse consequences for human or ecological systems, recognising the diversity of values and objectives associated with such system”. Thereby, climate risk, or in our context, wildfire risk, results “from the dynamic interactions between climate-related hazards with the exposure and vulnerability of the affected human or ecological system” (IPCC, 2022b, p.132). See Figure 1 for a conceptual illustration.

Figure 1 Wildfire risk as an intersection of hazard, exposure and vulnerability. Illustration based on IPCC (2022b) with extensions.

Building on the notion that wildfire risk emerges at the intersection of hazard, exposure and vulnerability, wildfires can be considered as **socio-natural hazards**, as they are determined both by natural and anthropogenic factors such as ecosystem degradation and climate change (UNDRR, 2022a). While a noticeable reduction in the number and size of fires was observed since the 1980s in the most affected countries, averages vary greatly over the years, the length of the fire season has increased as a result of climate change, with extreme events occurring in June and October, months that used to be outside the traditional fire season (Rego et al., 2018). While climate change increases and intensifies fire seasons in the Mediterranean region, changing temperatures and precipitation patterns also increase wildfire risk in central and northern Europe, regions commonly considered less prone to fires until now (Arnell et al., 2021; Gazzard et al., 2016). In addition to the climatic and weather conditions, wildfire hazard is subject to a socioeconomic dimension. Rural depopulation, farmland abandonment and concomitant afforestation has led to a significant increase in the amount of fuel shifting fire regimes in Southern Europe by reshaping the vegetation (Moreira et al., 2011; S. Oliveira et al., 2017; Pausas & Fernández-Muñoz, 2012). Thus, unmanaged fuel-intensive landscapes have been expanding rapidly on abandoned agricultural and pasture lands in the European South (Ganteaume et al., 2013; Nunes & Lourenço, 2017), decreasing landscape heterogeneity and connecting areas of high fuel loads (Ascoli et al., 2021; Sil et al., 2019). The lack of effective land governance (Spadoni et al., 2023) and absence of profitable value-chains for the agriculture and forestry sectors (Rego et al., 2018) are considered the main determinants of the significant rates of rural depopulation observed in Southern Europe.

Ecological change in ways other than land abandonment can also determine wildfire risk. The replacement of natural vegetation with extensive monocultures of highly flammable non-native species alters wildfire activity (Gómez-González et al., 2020; OECD, 2023). This has been observed in Portugal, where large-scale eucalyptus plantations established for economic reasons (Rego et al., 2013) have reduced the heterogeneity and increased the flammability of the landscape, fueling the occurrence of large-scale fires (Barquín et al., 2022).

Apart from economic objectives, there has been a rapid increase in plantations of fast growing and invasive species (Duane et al., 2021; McWethy et al., 2018), for biodiversity conservation, or the

enhancement of carbon sinks (Anderegg et al., 2020; Gómez-González et al., 2020; Hermoso et al., 2021). This may become an important driver of European wildfire risk, as the objectives of current and future EU climate and biodiversity regulations seem likely to foster an increase in flammable fuel loads. Moreover, fire suppression, which constitutes the dominant wildfire risk management approach across Europe (Rego et al., 2018), enhances fuel accumulation in many areas, facilitating the occurrence of extreme wildfire events, a phenomenon referred to as the *fire-paradox* (Calkin et al., 2014). This leads to a situation where a reliance on suppression strategies trades off short-term concerns with longer-term risks (S. Eriksen et al., 2021).

As a second component of climate risk, **exposure** refers to “*the situation of people, infrastructure, housing, production capacities and other tangible human assets located in hazard-prone areas*” (UNDRR 2022). The IPCC (2022, p. 2908) goes beyond this specification, explicitly mentioning also the presence of “*livelihoods; species or ecosystems, environmental functions, services and resources*”, as well as “*cultural assets*”. Thus, exposure refers to the location of the problem, which, in the context of wildfires is the area where fires occur or are expected to occur with a high likelihood and adjacent regions affected by smoke or other indirect impacts during or after wildfire occurs. Empirical evidence from European research is finding that socioeconomic inequalities such as rural poverty, aging, economic deprivation, unemployment and deregulated urban expansion are associated with wildfire occurrence (De Diego et al., 2023; Ferrara et al., 2019). It is important to note that in some European countries rural populations have lower poverty or social exclusion rates than those in urban areas; eg Spain, Portugal, France, Austria (Eurostat, 2022). However, this general picture can hide pockets of deprivation and some groups, in particular the Roma, can be subject to systematic discrimination and marginalisation with the result that they can be forced to occupy high hazard locations (Alexandrescu et al., 2021), including areas prone to natural disasters (Heidegger & Wiese, 2020). This highlights that wildfire exposure across Europe needs to be considered in concert with societal structures and inequalities.

We categorise exposure of different entities:

i) Exposure of people, their health, private assets and cultural heritage valuable to them

Over the period from 1945-2016, a total of 366 civilians, 266 firefighters and 263 people associated with managing the fires (such as plane crews, forest service officials, army personnel, etc.) lost their lives due to wildfires in Spain, Portugal, Greece and Sardinia, with a significant share of deaths attributed to burns and suffocation (Molina-Terrén et al., 2019). In addition to lives lost in the flames, mortality related to wildfire smoke is substantial. A study by Kollanus et al. (2017) estimates that in 2005 and 2008 a total of 1500 and 1100 premature deaths were attributable to vegetation fire PM2.5 across Europe, numbers that clearly exceed the deaths from direct exposure to flames.

Evidence obtained after the 2012 wildfire west of the Spanish city of Valencia shows an increase in respiratory symptoms in children exposed to wildfire smoke, with a particularly strong impact on individuals with asthma or rhinitis (Vicedo-Cabrera et al., 2016). Health effects of wildfires are also significant in older population cohorts in Spain, affecting not only respiratory health, but also psychological well-being (Caamano-Isorna et al., 2011).

In addition to health impacts affecting the integrity of individuals, wildfires cause damage to and loss of

private property, especially in areas where human settlements and natural vegetation intermingle, commonly referred to as the Wildland-Urban Interface (WUI) (Ganteaume et al., 2021). Poor land use planning has left the urban-rural interface with scattered and sparsely clustered buildings amongst shrubby vegetation, which is particularly prone to high-intensity fires (Beltrán-Marcos et al., 2023). Also, unclear zoning and outdated hazard maps are considered to have contributed to settlement expansion into flammable landscapes, increasing the exposure of people and their assets (OECD, 2023; Triantis, 2023). Wildfires spreading across the Mediterranean WUI, such as the 2018 fire occurring in Mati, Greece destroying 1000 structures and damaging more than 2500 properties, show the destructive potential of fires occurring in residential areas (Vacca et al., 2020). This is particularly the case for informal structures – those without building permits. During the 2018 Mati wildfires in Greece, assets without building permits amounted to a significant share of building losses (Blandford, 2019; OECD, 2023). This includes the exposure of poor and marginalized individuals (e.g. refugee camps or Roma settlements) (JRC, 2023), displaced from regular accommodation towards marginal and hazardous peripheries accompanied by their concomitant invisibility, preclude them from taking adaptation measures (Alexandrescu et al., 2021). Despite the lack of peer-reviewed literature connecting European wildfire risk and slum or informal settlements, we want to draw attention to this largely unaddressed issue. This form of environmental racism has so far received little attention in European legislation or policymaking, violating human rights and exacerbating the exposure of communities highly vulnerable to climate-related hazards and natural disasters (Heidegger & Wiese, 2020), such as wildfires.

Moreover, wildfires pose a threat to cultural heritage and archaeological sites across Europe, many of which are in close proximity to flammable vegetation, exposing them to wildfire hazard (Mallinis et al., 2016).

ii) Exposure of economic activity and productive assets

In the 2021 fire season, a quarter of the area affected by wildfires across Europe was agricultural land (JRC, 2022), indicating the exposure of agricultural production and workforce to wildfires. With most fires in Europe occurring between June and October, significant damages occur especially to permanent crops (up to 70%), like olive tree orchards or vines, with major importance for the affected rural economies (Stougiannidou & Zafeiriou, 2021a). Also, large fires have been threatening black pine afforestation across southern Europe, which represent an important source of income for rural communities (Alcasena et al., 2016). The impact of wildfires on economic activities goes beyond agricultural primary production. Otrachshenko & Nunes (2022) find a persistent negative relationship between burned areas and the number of tourist arrivals in Portugal, suggesting that the impact of a fire on the local tourism sector can extend over years.

iii) Exposure of ecosystems and their services.

Although constituting an integral part of fire prone ecosystems across Europe (Rego et al., 2018), defining the ecologically natural fire regime is difficult, due to the absence of historical data on timing and frequency of fires (Beckage et al., 2005). Also, prevalent ecosystems are not adapted to changing fire behaviour characterised by an increase in fire frequency, magnitude and intensity witnessed over the last years (Rego et al., 2018). During the 2021 fire season, 100 km² of Natura 2000 areas burned, with Italy and Spain accounting for 45% of this the total area burnt in protected areas experiencing fires sweeping through protected forests, such as the black pine forests across Southern Europe.

Recent evidence also highlights the impact of forest fires on ecosystem services by changing landscapes, leading to increased erosion and associated rockfall and landslide risk (Santi & Rengers, 2022; Sarro et al., 2021). Moreover, wildfires reduce the forests' carbon storage and therefore compromise climate mitigation strategies by interfering with the terrestrial carbon balance (Le Page et al., 2013). Seidl et al. (2014) show that forest fires conflict with afforestation strategies aiming to increase global carbon sinks in the quest of reaching net-zero emissions.

As the third dimension of wildfire risk, **vulnerability** is a socially constructed concept, changing with time and across communities and individuals (Jurgilevich et al., 2017; Kienberger et al., 2013). Following the UNDRR (2023), vulnerability is understood as *'the conditions determined by physical, social, economic and environmental factors or processes which increase the susceptibility [...] to the impacts of hazards'*. Research commonly assesses vulnerability to climate impacts or extreme weather on one-dimensional determinants (e.g. wealth & income (Hallegatte et al., 2020; Tasri et al., 2022), health (Chan et al., 2019), gender (Rahman, 2013), education (Muttarak & Lutz, 2014), at the risk of disregarding the interactions among them (Versey, 2021). Originating from the work of Crenshaw (1989) in the field of black feminist and civil rights research, the concept of intersectionality can provide a more nuanced understanding of social vulnerability (Kuran et al., 2020). Spreading beyond the field of race and gender, intersectionality has become established as a valuable concept for studying climate vulnerability (Kaijser & Kronsell, 2014), avoiding binary categorisations and enhancing understanding of the causes, and co-existence and synergisms, of multiple types of vulnerability (Kuran et al., 2020). Thus, in line with Kuran et al 2020 (p.6), *we understand "vulnerability as an intersectional phenomenon with a dynamic dimension"*, acknowledging the need to understand the role of individual characteristics, as well as their intersection, in determining the vulnerability of groups in the context of wildfires. Thereby, we acknowledge that vulnerability is not solely determined by material coping capacities, but requires an understanding of underlying systemic social injustices (Eriksen et al., 2020; Wisner et al., 2004). This emphasizes the multidimensional and context-specific nature of vulnerability and the inability to capture it in a single or static measure (Thomas et al., 2019). Table 1 collects major determinants of vulnerability to wildfires relevant in the European context.

These range from socioeconomic deprivation resulting in a lack of private, but also social safety nets (Lambrou et al., 2023), to the economic reliance on sectors prone to be affected (Otrachshenko & Nunes, 2022; Stougiannidou & Zafeiriou, 2021b) or ecosystem and regulating services disrupted by wildfires (Chuvieco et al., 2014; Román et al., 2013). A recent review by Lambrou et al. (2023) emphasizes the role of insufficient financial resources in exacerbating wildfire risk in the absence of effective institutional support during response and recovery among the most vulnerable communities. Wildfires pose a particular risk to rural communities dependent on small-scale farming (Rodrués et al., 2023). Fires sweeping permanent crops such as olive orchards (Stougiannidou & Zafeiriou, 2021b), or commercial forests (Alcasena et al., 2016) are destroying decades of revenue streams, disrupting farm livelihoods. In Portugal, where the tourism industry constitutes an important pillar in the national economy, accounting for approximately one tenth of national GDP and total employment (Otrachshenko & Nunes, 2022), wildfires pose an extraordinary risk when occurring in tourist areas, threatening a significant share of economic value added and employment opportunities.

Next to economic factors and socioeconomic status, rural depopulation has reduced social cohesion and the sense of neighbourhood among ageing villages and communities (Nunes & Lourenço, 2017; A. Rodrigues et al., 2022), which is found to have an impact on their capacities to cope with wildfire risk (Uyttewaal et al., 2023). Among rural areas, poor risk literacy resulting in the lack of preparation and awareness (Rodrigues et al., 2022) contributes to fire risk. This is particularly dangerous in situations where people with mobility constraints, health conditions or elevated vulnerability to smoke exposure, e.g. children (Vicedo-Cabrera et al., 2016) are exposed to flames or smoke. Also gender determines vulnerability, with empirical evidence revealing that women are associated with a lack of preparedness (Zabaniotou et al., 2021) and lower levels of self-reported risk perception (Oliveira et al., 2020).

As a result of different degrees of vulnerability, damages and losses may differ across similarly exposed individuals or assets, indicating a complex interdependency between the severity of a wildfire event and the impacts it causes to the affected society and environment (Tedim et al., 2018). A comprehensive understanding of the relevant aspects of vulnerability and their role in determining coping and adaptive capacities (Joakim et al., 2015) is becoming increasingly important in light of increasing wildfire severity and the growing need to cope with extreme wildfire events. Future WFRM will thus have to recognize the role of differential vulnerability and intersectionality on individual wildfire risk and account for differences in coping and adaptive capacities when designing risk reduction and financing schemes.

Table 1 Determinants of vulnerability in the context of European wildfire risk

Determinant for vulnerability	Description	References
Socioeconomic status	Unemployment, social and financial deprivation and low societal status reduce risk literacy and coping capacities	(De Diego et al., 2023; Ferrara et al., 2019; Lambrou et al., 2023)
Economic dependence	Reliance on economic sectors that are highly impacted by wildfires: agriculture, forestry, tourism.	(Otrachshenko & Nunes, 2022; Stougiannidou & Zafeiriou, 2021b)
Reliance on forest ecosystem and regulating services	Importance of timber, biofuels and amenity values. Impacts from increased soil erosion on regulating services. Loss of protected plant and animal species.	(Chuvienco et al., 2014; Román et al., 2013)
Social cohesion	Lower sense of neighbourhood decreases communities' capacities to cope	(Nunes & Lourenço, 2017; A. Rodrigues et al., 2022; Uyttewaal et al., 2023)
Risk literacy	Influx of urban population inexperienced with dealing with wildfires or ageing population unaware of changing fire regimes	(A. Rodrigues et al., 2022)
Age or pre-existing health condition	Particular vulnerability to wildfire smoke among elderly, children, people with pre-	(Climate-ADAPT, n.a.; Vicedo-Cabrera et al., 2016)

	existing cardiovascular or respiratory conditions	
Gender	Gender-related differences in preparedness and risk perception	(Oliveira et al., 2020; Zabaniotou et al., 2021)

We acknowledge, that the aspects mentioned in this section account for only some of the complexity related to socioeconomic dynamics shaping wildfire hazard, exposure and vulnerability and that wildfire risk is highly context specific and shaped by the underlying cultural and socioeconomic system. While we value this body of literature and the contribution it has made to shedding light on the social dimension of wildfire risk globally, this document focuses on aspects with a direct relevance to wildfires in Europe. Thus, we disregard processes and well-established phenomena determining changing fire regimes in different regional contexts. For example, in many parts of the world, colonising and development processes have resulted in the loss of, or major changes to, traditional land and fire management practices (Christianson, 2015; Eriksen & Hankins, 2014; Moura et al., 2019). There has also been a range of additional related structural and historical processes including neo-liberalism driving the creation of vulnerabilities, exposure and the associated power imbalances (Eriksen, 2007; Hoffman et al., 2022; Joseph et al., 2021; Wisner et al., 2004). As mentioned earlier, there are groups within Europe, such as the Roma, who illustrate processes creating powerlessness; while other processes such as weak development regulation, facilitate creation of new development in hazardous areas.

2.2 Managing wildfire risk

Figure 2 Integrated fire management embedded into fire management cycle, bringing together human, physical and ecological elements. Source: Rego et al. 2018

Effective WRM strategies address risk emerging at the intersection of hazard, exposure and vulnerability (indicated by the green area in Figure 1).

In the context of wildfire risk, management options are broad, ranging from financial tools like insurance to technological options, like aerial firefighting (Molina-Terrén et al., 2019), or building requirements (Alexandre et al., 2015), to promoting the ecological health of forests or behavioural changes in management practices (Dombeck et al., 2004).

In line with the steps of disaster risk management (i.e. prevention, preparedness, response, impacts and restoration & adaptation), holistic approaches to integrated fire management combine prevention and suppression strategies, taking into account different objectives of forestry, rural development, agriculture, climate and energy policies while ensuring safety of people and housing, and maintaining economic and ecosystem integrity (Rego et al., 2018). Thus, integrated fire management strategies involve each step within the management cycle, bringing together human, physical and ecological elements, see

Figure 2 for a conceptual overview (Rego et al., 2018). Challenging the proposed and commonly used categorization of phases in the fire management cycle, we acknowledge adaptation to changing circumstances as an integral part across all steps in WFRM. While the opportunity for major change commonly presents itself after a major event, bringing aspects of building back better to the table, an emphasis of pro-active adaptive action in line with the concept of *living with fire* may be more effective in mitigating the loss and suffering from wildfire occurrence in the first place (Montiel Molina & Galiana-Martín, 2016; Rego et al., 2018). In addition, holistic WFRM requires the consideration of the interconnectedness and interdependency between wildfire risk components (hazard, exposure, vulnerability) and the disaster risk management stages. For a comprehensive overview of potential trade-offs and synergies, see section 2 in Firelogue D4.1 (Plana et al., 2022).

Each year, public funding is supporting fuel management through cleaning forests and the maintenance of existing or building of new fuel breaks to prevent fire outbreaks and reduce the spread of fires across Europe (Rego et al., 2018). Yet, so far, spending is dominantly attributed towards fire suppression, rather than prevention in European countries. An investigation of the 2018 Calci fire in the province of Pisa, Italy, estimates the total costs of fire suppression at 1.5 million Euro, equivalent to 1 400 Euro per hectare burnt, with about 80% of the total costs spent on aerial resources (PREVAIL, 2020). Yet, such costly suppression approaches have shown a limited effectiveness when it comes to fighting the spread of extreme wildfires, exhibiting fire intensities that can be set under control only when weather conditions improve to facilitate firefighting (San-Miguel-Ayanz et al., 2013)

Figure 3 Integration of Firelogue WGs across the wildfire management cycle. Source: Rego et al. 2018 with extensions.

Current WFRM across Europe is heavily reliant on reactive management, focussing on wildfire suppression, with an increasing effort in and helping communities to prepare, cope and manage impacts (Alcasena et al., 2016; Otero & Nielsen, 2017). This strategy of coping has been effective for fire suppression in normal weather conditions, decreasing the overall number of fires and area burned (Rego et al., 2018) and may thus be suitable in areas with high fire experience and with few social or ecological assets at risk (McWethy et al., 2019). However, the increase in magnitude and severity of fires is challenging prevailing wildfire management strategies across Europe (Rego et al., 2018).

While tweaking current practices by stepping up efforts in fuel management, prescribed burning, and community planning to reduce, or wherever possible, avoid exposure, and improve evacuation or sheltering may help to overcome the current adaptation frontier by shifting soft adaptation limits, the long-term effectiveness of such approaches is increasingly debated.

For supporting the development of more efficient and integrated solutions to European WFRM, Firelogue establishes 5 WGs for informing coordinated and cooperative decision making supported by evidence-based research by the IAs. Firelogue WGs tie on different phases along the fire management cycle, ensuring a comprehensive analysis of management strategies across all phases. See Figure 3 for an overview of WG coverage across the fire management cycle.

2.3 Embedding WFRM into the relevant socio-economic context

The tight human-environment interdependencies between communities, landscapes and regional scales make wildfire management a multilevel environmental governance challenge (Fischer et al., 2016; Hamilton et al., 2019; Palsa et al., 2022; Spies et al., 2014). As fires spread across management jurisdictions, effective risk mitigation requires cooperation and coordination between land managers, users, municipalities and private landowners in areas where public land management authority is limited (Ager et al., 2017; Champ et al., 2012; Charnley et al., 2020). With due regard to these suggestions in peer-reviewed literature, Firelogue understands WFRM as a shared responsibility, acknowledging the importance of bringing together the multitude of different WFRM stakeholders to uncover their potential synergistic and conflicting interests, perceptions of injustices, aims, and means.

Actors in WFRM

Based on a survey conducted among the IAs and FirEUrisk aiming to enhance the understanding of their scope and identify relevant areas for knowledge sharing and joint activities, a comprehensive WFRM

Figure 4 Proposed stakeholder clustering for Firelogue. Martín, Juan, et al. 2022, p. 27

stakeholder map has been compiled (for a more in-depth report on the survey results see *D1.1 Review report of IA case studies including wildfire events, actors, WFRM measures, technologies and SOPs*).

Building on the proposed stakeholder clustering by individual IAs and FireEUrisk, the combined mapping illustrated in Figure 4 is holistic and integrative, grouping stakeholders into 8 overarching categories, consisting of different stakeholder profiles each, either directly or indirectly involved in WFRM (Martín, Juan, et al., 2022) :

(1) *Emergency management organisations* refer to operational practitioners involved in response operations at the forefront of wildfire incidents.

(2) *Scientific community* encompasses research and academic institutions involved in diverse scientific areas related to wildfire risk management, such as fire ecology, landscape management, risk governance, forest economy, rural policy, or civil protection.

(3) *Policy-making bodies* involve stakeholders who have a key role in influencing strategic choices for wildfire management and, therefore, become enshrined in territorial policies.

(4) *Land management groups* refer to those stakeholders who have the capacity to conduct management actions on the territory, either because they own it or because they hold the right to act on it.

(5) *Environmental associations* are devoted to the study of the natural environment, the protection of the landscape and ecosystems, and enforcing society's awareness of environmental issues via education.

(6) *Media refers to communicators* with the capacity to reach many people and, therefore, influence people's opinions, beliefs, and attitudes toward wildfire management policies.

(7) *Society* encompasses citizens and groups of citizens whose education on a fire risk culture is fundamental to improving society's resilience to wildfires.

(8) *Industry, technology, and innovation* involve several industrial sectors with a key role in providing safety and adaptive capacity resulting from wildfire events.

A more detailed description of the stakeholder groups can be found in *D7.2 Stakeholder clustering report* (Martín, Vendrell, et al., 2022).

Identification of conflicting interests: real and perceived injustices

Wildfires occurring in urban interface areas (also known as the WUI) pose significant governance challenges, with different perspectives of the underlying problem and different perceptions of what mitigating wildfire risk entails (Champ et al., 2012; Rittel & Webber, 1973). Constituting socially complex phenomena, concerns regarding ecological, social or political aspects of WFRM differ among stakeholder groups, leading to differences in the acceptance of management practices (Carroll et al., 2007; McCaffrey et al., 2008). Champ et al. (2012), stress the importance of recognising and accounting for the differences in risk mitigation and related power dynamics and the importance of ensuring a working relationship with communities and external stakeholders.

In light of these challenges, Firelogue brings together different actors in WFRM, acknowledging potential conflicts of interests and synergies along different phases of the risk management cycle. As the synthesis of survey results among IAs and FireEUrisk conducted in D1.1 (Martín, Juan, et al., 2022) reveals, the surveyed experts see considerable potential for conflicts in their case study work related to community preparedness and land-use changes. All the respondents indicated the lack of community preparedness or proactive attitudes as the main conflict, emphasising the role an increasing population living in or visiting the WUI, their lack of risk culture, and the capacity to undertake preventive and self-protection measures. Also, land-use changes (e.g., land abandonment, soil sealing in dense housing developments, agriculture intensification...) are considered as a substantial conflict by all the projects. This issue is especially relevant in wildfire risk within the Mediterranean regions, where land changes that occurred over the last century have led to an increase in fuel loads in the landscape, which is altering the fire regimes and emanating into more extreme and catastrophic events. Land ownership, devaluation of forest resources, policy and legal barriers, and the confrontation between conservation and productive management were considered the main issues by most projects. As prescribed burns are becoming more recognised in the European WFRM community, burning restrictions were only considered as a potential conflict by only one of the projects.

To proactively address potential conflicts and harness possible synergies between different actors (or stakeholder groups), it is key to identify and understand what these diverse actors and stakeholder groups perceive as just outcomes and just processes in WFRM, as there might be very different ideas of justice at work in different fire-prone communities and among their diverse members. Building on McCauley & Heffron (2018) and on the broader environmental justice literature (e.g., Ramirez-Andreotta, 2019), we identify three domains of justice that need to be considered in the WG discussions for understanding potential conflicts in the transition to integrated and inclusive WFRM approaches: distributional justice, procedural justice and restorative justice. For a more elaborate review of different justice dimensions and their implications for WFRM see Firelogue Deliverable 4.1 (Plana et al., 2022).

3. Horizontal structure of WG exchange: the 4 Thematic Strands (TS)

To structure discussions in the dialogue formats, WGs work along four horizontal thematic strands to ensuring a parallel process and to facilitating cross-working group exchange. More precisely, all WGs address the following aspects of WFRM within and across their respective foci: socioeconomic, climate policy (mitigation and adaptation), technology, and earth observation. The thematic strands have been chosen to reflect main policy aspects (socio-economic aspects as well as aspects of climate policy, Workshop Cycle I) that are taken into consideration when designing WFRM strategies or approaches in and across the different WGs. In addition, facilitators of respective WFRM approaches such as technologies and earth observation have been selected (Workshop Cycle II). Thereby, Firelogue accommodates the call to integrate socioeconomic and climate aspects, while technologies and earth observation services serve as main means of facilitating integrated WFRM approaches.

3.1 IA and WG integration

Based on the IA and FireEURisk survey results, Martín, Juan, et al. (2022) , carve out topics for discussion across the five sectorial WGs, listed in Figure 5. Topics raised for discussion in the *environmental and ecology WG* cover primarily scenarios of future fire risk, including wildfire prevention, the creation of fire resilient landscapes, and the promotion of ecosystem restoration and adaptation. Overarching topics related to the *societal WG* mention the role of socio-economic activities and impacts, people’s safety and related preparedness strategies. For the *infrastructure WG*, projects stress topics related to policy and planning tools to improve the protection of major infrastructure assets and on the cooperation with the different infrastructures authorities, including transport, energy, and water. Few projects reported topics for the *insurance WG*, pointing out the general topic of insurance mechanisms and new insurance parametrisation. Finally, topics proposed for the *civil protection WG* are related to other WGs, raising social aspects (e.g., public awareness or citizens engagement), as well as aspects of effective emergency management. For a more elaborate discussion of the scope of each project and WG topics raised, see section 4.6 in Martín, Juan, et al. (2022) .

Figure 5 Main topics for WG discussions proposed by projects. Source: Martín, Juan, et al. (2022) , p.33.

3.2 Horizontal integration of WG discussions: TS Factsheets

Figure 6 Illustration of the horizontal integration of Workshop cycles I and II along the TS. Arrows indicate the main sources for TS input into WG exchange. IA & FireURisk innovations are important especially in Workshop cycle II.

To support dialogue formats within and across WGs, thematic guidance is offered through the four thematic strands: socioeconomic, climate change mitigation and adaptation, technology and earth observation. Based on expertise, desk research and insights gathered from the survey conducted among IAs and FireURisk, the TS Factsheets outline their suggestions for guiding WG exchange, introducing their overarching topic and breaking down aspects and topics with respect to their relevance for each WG. With TS involvement in the planning of WG exchange and post workshop analysis, Factsheets will be continuously refined and adjusted to accommodate Firelogue’s findings. IA & FireURisk generated knowledge on WFRM innovations will be important in the development and concretization of topics under

the TS Technology and Earth Observation, building the basis for WG discussions in Workshop cycle II. See Figure 6 for an illustration of the integration of TS Factsheets, Workshop Cycles and IA & FireURisk innovations.

The current versions of the individual TS Factsheets are included in the following.

Factsheet 1

Socioeconomic Thematic Strand (IIASA)

Authors and contact: Eva Preinfalk, John Handmer, Thomas Schinko | contact: preinfalk@iiasa.ac.at

Purpose & Key definitions

This Factsheet sets out the background and approach used by the socioeconomic Thematic Strand (TS) to develop a common understanding of possible socioeconomic futures in wildfire risk assessment. We use the well-established SSPs (Shared Socio-economic Pathways) to **explore alternative socioeconomic futures and their implications for designing effective wildfire risk management (WFRM)**. With both climate change and socio-economic drivers increasing future wildfire risk, wildfire adaptation will have to adopt effective strategies to mitigate risk, while preserving the livelihoods and wellbeing of those affected, and limiting carbon release and ecosystem damage.

We understand *socioeconomic* as an umbrella term for “a wide range of aspects of societal, or more broadly, socioecological systems”, including “demographic, political, social, cultural, institutional, life-style, economic, and technological aspects, and the conditions of ecosystems and ecosystem services that have been affected by human activity such as air and water quality, biodiversity, and ecosystem form and function”, and thereby explicitly exclude “conditions related to future climate change itself”¹.

Rationale: Why focus on socioeconomics in WFRM?

The importance of socioeconomic dynamics in the formation of climate risk is well recognised². However, biophysical factors still dominate assessments of future climate risk³, even though the planning and design of effective adaptation measures requires a comprehensive understanding not only of climatic drivers, but also of the interaction between hazards and future societies and economies⁴.

To this date, the dominant management approaches largely neglect the complexity and contemporary nature of wildfire risk in a world undergoing constant climate and socioeconomic change, taking insufficient account of the diversity of areas prone to fire now and in the future⁶. In addition to climatic drivers, demography, socioeconomic and institutional factors, settlement patterns, agricultural land-use, forestry practices and implemented risk management strategies are fundamental to determining wildfire. This TS emphasizes the importance of accounting for these socioeconomic determinants of wildfire risk across different socioeconomic pathways and thereby supports Firelogue’s approach of accommodating different WFRM related futures across WGs.

A common understanding of possible socioeconomic futures in WFRM

Given that uncertainty related to socioeconomic development is a major determinant of future European wildfire risk, we present a set of plausible narratives through qualitative descriptions of future societal and economic development. These build on the established concept of Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs)¹, which are conceptualised as global narratives^{1,7} and have been extended for the European context as *EUR-SSPs*⁸. We use three of the five SSPs, covering the most decisive differences relevant in the context of WFRM. The narratives differ with respect to their trends in population, economic development, institutional effectiveness, equity, environmental concern and ecosystem wellbeing and thus span a sufficiently broad spectrum for assessing future wildfire risk and the challenges of designing adaptive WFRM strategies.

The narratives we introduce here relate to (EUR-)SSP1, a *sustainable Europe* with rapid technological and economic progress and low inequalities, contrasted with (EUR-) SSP5, a *carbon-intensive Europe*, where rapid technological and economic progress is supported by carbon-based fuels⁸. In addition, (EUR-)SSP3, a *divided Europe*, accounts for a future that is characterized by high levels of inequality, environmental degradation and the failure of institutions⁸. See *Table 1* for more details on the socioeconomic futures and differentiation among them.

Table 2 Qualitative descriptions of socioeconomic futures considered⁸

	<i>A sustainable Europe</i>	<i>A divided Europe</i>	<i>A carbon intensive Europe</i>	
Narrative	Sustainable economic growth through effective governments and cooperation. More equal societies adopt less resource intensive lifestyles, enabled by a progressing energy transition.	Europe is fragmented with strong regional rivalry and inequalities between and within countries. Production is carbon and resource intensive, causing severe ecosystem failures.	Fossil-fuelled growth stimulates economic wealth, at the expense of environmental degradation. There is strong faith in technological solutions manage social and ecological problems.	
Key elements related to WFRM	Economic development	Gradual, increasingly equitable growth	Low, high inequality	High, increasing wealth
	Environmental policies	Effective sustainable solutions	No priority, ineffective	No priority, ineffective
	Social cohesion	High	Low across EU, higher within countries	High
	Quality of governance	High, sustainability focus	Low and ineffective	High, business focus
	Technology development	High, but not pervasive	Low	Strong, crucial
	Human capital investment (health & education)	High	Low	High

Implications for future wildfire risk and the design of WFRM strategies

Accounting for these uncertainties and dynamics in the socioeconomic system is crucial for future WFRM planning, as risk assessments based on historical trends may become inefficient and misleading. See *Figure 1* for an illustrative conceptualization of potential socioeconomic dynamics to consider when designing WFRM.

A major factor in **wildfire hazard** across Europe is rural land abandonment^{9,10}. In a *sustainable Europe*, where development stays within environmental boundaries and land use is strongly regulated¹¹, rural abandonment due to ecosystem degradation or the spread of invasive species has a small impact on hazard. This is in contrast to a *divided Europe*, where almost no land-use regulation leads to serious possibly irreversible ecosystem degradation. High rates of agricultural intensification and yield increases in a *sustainable Europe* raise wealth, reducing rural land abandonment relative to a *divided Europe*, where low agricultural intensification reduces sectoral incomes.

Figure 7 Illustration of how socioeconomic processes affect the dimensions of wildfire risk.

institutions, low education and technological development in the agricultural sector increases exposure of economic activity and livelihoods in a *divided Europe*.

Exposure to wildfire of private assets and economic production largely depends on the level of urban sprawl and the importance of agricultural production as a share of gross economic value added. Population and income growth increase exposure most significantly in a *carbon-intensive Europe*, positive population and income growth rates prevail also in a *sustainable Europe*¹². Insufficient land use management and planning in a *divided* and *carbon-intensive Europe* lead to an increase in sprawl⁷. High levels of urbanization, education and income growth reduces the reliance on primary production and thus exposure of economic production in a *sustainable Europe*, whereas poor

As a major determinant of the capacity to cope with wildfires, **vulnerability** due to socioeconomic status is lower in futures with high economic growth, increased wealth and effective institutions, compared to a *divided Europe*. Insufficient healthcare capacities in a *divided Europe*, where countries are burdened with climate-related health effects¹³, increase the risk especially for vulnerable groups. Poor levels of education, alongside dysfunctional institutions increase wildfire impacts on livelihoods and economic well-being, particularly in a *divided* future^{7,14}. High levels of ecosystem degradation and thus high risk of disruption by wildfire further increases vulnerability of sectors reliant on provisioning ecosystem functions especially in a *divided Europe*, whereas improved environmental conditions and strong regulations avoiding environmental tradeoffs reduce this vulnerability in a *sustainable Europe*.

Conclusions & implications for WG discussions: What can we deduce for future WFRM?

In light of the socioeconomic uncertainties discussed above, robust and effective wildfire adaptation pathways are flexible and transformational in nature, avoiding lock-ins and maladaptation from maintaining conventional wildfire risk management strategies. With climate change and socio-economic drivers increasing future wildfire risk, wildfire adaptation will have to acknowledge exposure and vulnerability, adopting effective strategies to mitigate risk, while preserving the livelihoods and wellbeing of those affected, and also limiting carbon release and ecosystem damage.

Adhering to the concepts of adaptive policymaking^{15,16} and adaptation pathways¹⁷, we conceptualize a multidimensional possibility space illustrated via three plausible future socioeconomic futures for designing dynamic adaptive policy pathways for managing future wildfire risk. Thereby, adaptation planning should pursue a strategic vision, while committing to short-term actions and establishing a suitable framework for guiding future actions¹⁸.

Table 2: Suggested points for discussion for WG exchange based on the topics proposed by IAs and FireEURisk. The points raised aim to support a strategic and flexible design of WFRM policy pathways that accounts for the uncertainty of socioeconomic dynamics.

	Topic 1 (Economic dimension)	Topic 2 (Environmental dimension)	Topic 3 (Social/Justice dimension)
Environmental & Ecology WG	Economic role of ecosystem services	Requirements for effective post-fire restoration	Winners/losers from ecosystem restoration
Societal WG	Preservation of livelihoods & critical industries	Environmental concern	Differential vulnerabilities, intersectionality
Infrastructure WG	Role of the public sector and public-private partnerships	Conflicts: infrastructure & environment	Liability in case of unintended, unfavourable outcome
Insurance WG	Feasibility of reinsurance & public sector involvement	Insurance as incentive for ecosystem preservation	Affordability of insurance products & adaptive capacities of communities
Civil Protection WG	Financial capacities to prepare & adapt	Conflicts: civil protection & environmental objectives	Inclusivity of communication strategies

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Factsheet 2

Climate change mitigation and adaptation (CMCC)

Authors and contact: Jose Maria Costa Saura, Valentina Bacciu, Costantino Sirca and Donatella Spano | contact: costa.saura@cmcc.it

Purpose & Key definitions

This Factsheet sets out the background and approach used by the climate change mitigation and adaptation Thematic Strand (TS) to develop a common understanding, across working groups, of climate change policies in Europe that are potentially linked with wildfire risk management (WFRM). This TS aims to review main European policies related to climate change to explore and discuss potential synergies and conflicts across WFRM phases and stakeholders. Furthermore, we present some key principles for good adaptation that can be considered for designing/studying innovative measures for WFRM (e.g. IAs case studies) to ensure that issues related to climate change are not neglected and making the measures potentially more consistent and fruitful in the mid and long term avoiding negative effects with other sectors.

Climate change policies are understood as plans, programs, rules, strategies and all set of measures aiming to fight climate change. Climate change policies cover both mitigation actions, i.e., aimed at reducing emissions, and adaptation, i.e., actions to prevent or minimise the impacts of climate change.

Why is Climate change mitigation and adaptation important in the context of WFRM?

Anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions are unequivocally related to global warming and alterations of precipitation patterns¹. Furthermore, human-induced climate change is affecting the frequency and magnitude of extreme weather events such as heat waves and droughts¹. As a consequence, fire danger is increasing worldwide, and especially in some European regions^{2, 3}. Rising temperatures and intense droughts are leading to greater fuel dryness making landscapes more prone to burn⁴. Furthermore, land use change (e.g., rural abandonment) is exacerbating the risk of extreme fire events because of a generalized decrease in landscape management ultimately leading to an increase in fuel loads^{5, 6}.

EU policies to face climate change and their link with WFRM

To face climate change in the European Union (EU), the European Green Deal sets the strategy to reach climate neutrality by 2050 aiming also to make Europe fully adapted to climate change impacts without leaving behind any person and place⁷. The European Green Deal includes a set of policies and measures to achieve the green transformation. Some already approved initiatives that cover the challenges posed by climate change are the “European climate law”, “the new EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change”, “the new EU forest strategy for 2030”, the “farm to fork strategy” or the “EU biodiversity strategy for 2030”.

All these initiatives recognise the central role of forests in adapting and mitigating climate change underlining their main contribution to achieve a sustainable and climate neutral economy while protecting the services provided by ecosystems⁸. Thus, WFRM might benefit from these initiatives since most of them are directly related to forest management (linked with reducing fuel loads) and disaster risk reduction to meet their objectives. For instance, the new EU forest strategy for 2030 promotes forest-based bio-

economies (e.g., wood and non-wood products, bioenergy, ecotourism...) stimulating forest management and potentially reversing trends associated to fire risk such as land abandonment (with new jobs and growth opportunities). Thus, these activities might help, for instance, to reduce fuel loads and vertical continuity making forests more fire resilient and fires easier to suppress⁹. Indeed, the new EU forest strategy for 2030 explicitly promotes “closer-to-nature forest management”¹⁰ and a voluntary certification scheme for guiding adaptation. Furthermore, the strategy underlines the need of financial drivers to increase forest resilience similarly to the Common Agricultural Policy which already provides economic support for preventing wildfires.

In line with the forest strategy, the new EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change also aims to ensure resilience but under the perspectives of both ecosystems and societies reducing the adverse consequences of climate change impacts. The strategy expects adaptation to be smart (robust data and tools), fast (providing resources for speed up the process) and systemic (covering all economic sectors and levels in the society). The strategy pursues resilient landscapes by adopting, among others, nature based solutions (e.g., silvo-arable agroforestry for wildfire protection¹¹). Furthermore, this EU policy aims to empower citizens for direct actions to adapt by taking advantage on existing initiatives, e.g., the EU Covenant of Mayors, and underlines the need to invest in climate-resilient infrastructures (see Technical guidance on the climate proofing of infrastructure in the period 2021-2027¹²). Also the new EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change highlights the need to create and promote new insurance products as a risk transfer mechanism to reduce disaster costs to taxpayers or governments. Thus, different themes important for WFRM are covered by the EU policies related to climate change.

The European Commission (EC) is also actively encouraging the development and implementation of national adaptation strategies (NAS) and plans (NAP) aiming to face climate change vulnerabilities and address medium and long term needs for adaptation across countries. Currently, country members are at different stages over this process with key information reported in the European Climate Adaptation Platform (Climate-ADAPT; <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/>). Note that Climate-ADAPT is the European authoritative platform for adaptation containing information about EU policies, tools and case studies). To achieve the expected goals when designing and implementing NAS, the EC suggests to follow a set of key principles¹³. It suggests that adaptation should be sustainable (i.e., not compromising other parts of the earth system), holistic (i.e., covering multiple stressors and affected sectors), tailored across geographical scales and sectors, flexible (i.e., potentially adjusted if climate trends change) and science-based. Furthermore, adaptation should be transparent, engage different actors and be reviewed continuously for potential improvements. In addition, it was underlined the importance of considering the complementarity between adaptation actions and mitigation policies, avoiding potential trade-offs and ensuring coherence between both aspects¹⁴.

Conclusions & implications for WG discussions: What can we deduce for future WFRM?

Awareness about EU policies and measures potentially related to wildfires might be of great importance for WFRM across sectors and stakeholders. The identification of potential synergies, conflicts, injustices and gaps between policies and target groups might be of great interest for discussion within/across WGs which aim to shape EU policies under principles of just transition (see deliverable D.4.1).

Furthermore, the key principles suggested by the EC for guiding adaptation can go beyond the NAS and be assimilated also for designing/studying innovative measures for WFRM. Indeed, the measures developed within the Innovation Actions funded by the EU might benefit of following these principles to ensure that climate change related issues are not neglected and making the measures more consistent and fruitful in the mid and long term. Discussing these measures under those principles within the WGs might help to set a picture of the status of current WFRM initiatives under the perspective of climate change.

Table 2: TS discussion topics proposed for WG exchange

	Topic 1 Awareness, perception, limitations, conflicts and synergies in CC related EU polices	Topic 2 Ways to speed up objectives in CC related EU polices	Topic 3 IAs measures under the perspective of climate change (flexibility, scalability, sustainability, systematic)
Environmental & Ecology WG	How do WG members perceive EU policies influence (e.g., forest-based bioeconomy) on WFRM?	Which mechanisms might speed up the transition to fire resilient landscapes?	Identification and discussion of potential win-win measures
Societal WG	Which opportunities/limitations the Societal WG members envision across EU mechanisms for local adaptation?		Inclusion of climate change perspective in citizen involvement strategies
Infrastructure WG	How to make that Infrastructure managers play a role in (and take advantage of) the EU objectives of building (fire) resilient landscapes and promote forest-based bioeconomy?	How to speed up investments in climate resilient infrastructures?	Are long term planning/measures considering climate change effects on risk?
Insurance WG	Do Insurance WG members identify limitations and opportunities in the EU strategy to close the climate protection gap?		Should insurance products consider mid/long term climate change scenarios?
Civil Protection WG	Potential drawbacks observed by civil protection WG members in EU measures for	How to make that civil protection play a role in (and take advantage of) the EU objectives of building (fire) resilient	Are operational capabilities across EU regions (e.g. northern countries) threatened under climate change?

	boosting economy in forested rural areas.	landscapes and promote forest-based bioeconomy?	
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Factsheet 3

Technology Thematic Strand (*INESCTEC*)

Authors and contact: Diana Viegas, Hugo Silva | contact: diana.viegas@inesctec.pt, hugo.m.silva@inesctec.pt

Purpose & Key definitions

This Factsheet defines a common framework used by Firelogue Thematic Strand (TS) on Technology, to foster a discussion across the working groups on how technology can help improve or challenge the approaches to Wildfire Risk Management. We are keen to foster the discussion on how technological developments with different technology readiness levels (TRL) in different areas of WFRM have been used and adopted within each working group topic.

The overall aim of this TS is to help foster the discussion and benchmark novel technological developments that are currently being developed and could potentially be implemented soon to accomplish the high-level impacts that were set by the EU in the IAs Green deal calls.

We define technology or technological developments as a set of tools that can be based on hardware or software components, sensors, or automated processes that are utilized to address different areas of WFRM.

Why is this topic important in the context of WFRM?

Throughout the years within the EU, a broad approach was applied to the wildfires problem and now most recently to extreme wildfires event. The EU has made a significant effort in the development of knowledge, methodologies, and technologies to address wildfire problems in the face of climate and environmental changes, as well as new social and cultural trends with growth dynamics. Examples of the advancement of EU instruments that have been playing a key role in fire knowledge, enhancing operational management, and supporting stakeholder decisions of tools and/or cooperation mechanisms are the European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS)ⁱ that provides fire weather forecasts, the DKMRC Risk Data Hubⁱⁱ for risk assessment on natural hazards, the Copernicus EMSⁱⁱⁱ (which EFFIS is now part of), the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS)^{iv} and the Copernicus Atmosphere Service (CAMS)^v that utilize earth observation data to detect/monitor events and provide support information.

A range of technologies has been developed to facilitate WFRM. Among others, future trends will develop more advanced techniques, models, solutions, and capabilities for preventing, predicting, monitoring, and fighting wildfires, and mitigating their impact, including better and advanced technologies, equipment, and decision support systems for first responders. However, some of them (i.e., modeling) can be subject to uncertainties that need to be put into context or bind several sectors together, for example when developing new risk transfer solutions also relating to cascading effects of infrastructure failure.

Furthermore, technologies can target the development of novel detection & response technologies by fostering an integrated approach using heterogeneous means including the joint efforts of sensors technology, ground sensors, and crowd-sourced information systems (Tavra et al, 2021), earth observation data^{vi} (Maxwald et al, 2022), early warning systems (Ayanz et al, 2012), communications systems (Leonor, 2018), and drone technology (Unmanned aerial Vehicle - UAV) (Partheepan et al, 2023), all combined into a single detection & response system capable of the forecast, detect and combat faster and efficiently ignitions before these become extreme fire events.

To foster the discussion of technological developments, the thematic strand proposed topics can be divided according to the following three dimensions to allow the discussion between Working Groups, see Figure 1:

- Disaster resilience communities [yellow colour]: Focus on the societal application of the technology (McCaffrey, 2015)
- Sustainable landscape [green colour]: Improved technology to support environmental monitoring, mainly in the preparedness, recovery, and mitigation scenarios
- Emergency management [red colour]: Technological tools that will help to manage a crisis event, more related to the response phase in the emergency cycle.

Figure 1. Technological Approach to WFRM based on Societal, Landscape and Emergency Management Topics

Conclusion & suggested points for discussion in WG exchange

Technology and Technological developments are at core of novel and most innovative ways to prevent, respond and recover from wildfires, and therefore are fundamental Disaster Risk Management tools to prevent, reduce and mitigate the negative impacts of wildfire on the ecosystems, peoples, and goods.

A potential way for working groups to start the discussion on technology and technological developments would be to list all major developments within their WG topic based on technological assets over the past decade, and if the technology or tools that were developed were adopted and by whom? Ideally this information could be crossed-checked with the technological developments that are being conducted by the IAs and other wildfires related projects to foster the discussion on the needs and requirements of these technologies to be adopted by the wildfire community and stakeholders.

Therefore, we propose to group the technological developments based on their end-application, namely on how these technologies can help people (making the disaster community more resilient), allow a more sustainable landscape, and help during the response phase and aftermath of the crisis management.

Examples of TS technological discussion topics are proposed in Table 2., for each working group but other topics can be added to the list based on expert group opinions and common interests.

Table 2: TS discussion topics proposed for WG exchange.

	Topic 1 Disaster Resilient Communities	Topic 2 Sustainable Landscape	Topic 3 Emergency Management
Environmental & Ecology WG	WUI (Wild-urban interface) ^{vii} Fire risk index Classification of vulnerable areas Self-assessment tools with mixed reality applications	Tool to supply fuel landscape management and ecosystem restoration data. Fuel Maps ^{viii} Improve vegetation index. Technological tools for post-fire analysis measurement of direct and indirect impacts	
Societal WG	Provide communities with science-based fire information knowledge. Tools to evaluate if the communities are at risk.	Crowdsource systems	Emergency response communications
Infrastructure WG	Tools to evaluate if the infrastructures are at risk in all states of the disaster risk cycle. Design fire safety assessments of buildings and infrastructures and with attention to new building materials with fire protection		Critical Infrastructures monitoring Prevention measurement Study of cascading effects
Insurance WG	How technology can help fire risk assessments Parametric insurance Artificial Intelligence Data Science as a tool to evaluate insurance risk parameters.		Assessment of direct and indirect impacts of wildfires and associated costs
Civil Protection WG	Evacuation plans Fire Risk Forecast / Resource Disposal Augmented Reality Simulation Tools		Enhance evolution forecast of wildfire risks: - Fire danger risk - Weather forecast - Early warning system - Historical data analysis - Improve emergency response tools (UAVs, smart garment tools) - Crowd source system

			- Training - Decision support systems
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i <https://effis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

ii <https://drmkc.jrc.ec.europa.eu/risk-data-hub#/>

iii <https://emergency.copernicus.eu/>

iv <https://land.copernicus.eu/>

v <https://atmosphere.copernicus.eu/>

vi <https://effis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/about-effis/technical-background/active-fire-detection>

vii <https://www.usfa.fema.gov/wui/what-is-the-wui.html>

viii <https://fire-res.eu/fireurisk-and-fire-res-sharing-knowledge-on-how-to-map-fuel-availability-at-the-european-level/>

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Factsheet 4

Earth Observation Thematic Strand (NOA)

Authors and contact: Mariza Kaskara, Haris Kontoes, Marietta Papakonstantinou | contact: kaskara@noa.gr

Purpose & Key definitions

This Factsheet sets out the background and approach used by the Earth Observation Thematic Strand (TS) to develop a common understanding of possible contribution of Earth Observation in wildfire risk assessment. This TS aspires to demonstrate earth observation features and their implications to the various WG topics for effective WFRM.

We define **“Earth Observation”** as the gathering of information about the Earth's surface, atmosphere, oceans, and land masses using a variety of remote sensing techniques and instruments. This can include the use of satellite imagery, aerial photography, and ground-based measurements. The data and information collected through earth observation can be used for a wide range of applications, such as monitoring natural resources, predicting weather and climate patterns, detecting and responding to natural disasters, and studying the effects of human activity on the environment. This information is useful for the researcher and for policy makers for the decision making for sustainable development, monitoring the environment and to forecast the natural hazard events.¹

Rationale: *Why is Earth Observation important in WFRM?*

Earth observation (EO) provides an effective way of exploring the physical, chemical, and biological information related to the Earth². EO satellite data are an indispensable tool to provide measurements and support for related environmental, social, political, and economic studies. From forecasting weather to monitoring disasters and the health of ecosystems, communities and citizens, EO data informs, locates and provides context to various sectors from research to policy-making including achieving sustainable societies³.

Moving beyond research, EO has the opportunity to contribute to some of the most pressing global societal challenges, such as those identified by the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. Satellite, airborne, and Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) acquisitions provide data at multiple scales for monitoring the state of natural ecosystems, natural resources, oceans, coasts, land, and built infrastructure as well as their changes over time⁷.

More specifically, EO data is also a critical tool of universal applicability for detecting, monitoring, and assessing the damaging impacts of wildfires^{8,9} and of post-fire soil erosion and loss potential¹⁰. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S034181621930462X>¹¹. Both optical and radar satellite remote sensing have proven to provide significant insight in wildfire events. The European Commission has developed the European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS) (<http://effis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>) to provide a fire risk forecast and a fire danger assessment in EU countries. EFFIS is one of the Copernicus Emergency Services and becomes an essential tool for providing most up-to

date information on fire danger in EU, identify the evolution of wildfires and help national authorities to monitor these wildfires¹².

In the past decades, several algorithms utilizing data from Earth observation satellites have been developed to assist wildfire risk management. The figure below depicts how EO services can contribute to the disaster risk management cycle and some examples of potential services in each phase.

Figure 1: Examples of EO services through the disaster risk management cycle

Much of the focus of disaster wildfire activity is currently on the response phase, during which rapid action can save lives. Satellite EO is a recognized solution for enabling more efficient relief actions and supporting aid actors with objective and up to date information. It is however widely accepted that increased efforts on risk reduction during the mitigation and preparedness phases of a wildfire will save more lives and protect property by reducing the exposure of populations to the hazard.

Earth observation in prevention, mitigation and preparedness

Preparedness efforts offer WFRM managers the best opportunity to save lives and protect property. Mitigation activity covers on-going monitoring of fire hazard and certain elements at risk. Comprehensive monitoring can lead to improved ability to warn before a wildfire strikes. Preparedness also refers to science work undertaken to better understand the nature of the risks involved. This is the case for example of fire modelling.

Below there are some indicative examples of how distinguished EO services that can assist before a fire occurs:

- 1) Enhanced Early Warning System, through short-term predictive fire risk maps by using Machine Learning (ML)-based models and/or fire danger rating system. Accurate next-day fire risk predictions can be produced and communicated to the Fire Services via daily fire risk probability maps.
- 2) Scenario-based fire-spread, considering ignition points and extreme wind characteristics. This is a process of simulating the spread of a fire under different scenarios, such as different weather patterns, fuel conditions, and topography. Scenario-based fire spread can be used to help predict the potential impact of a wildfire and to develop strategies for mitigating its effects.
- 3) Sub-seasonal and seasonal predictions of fire weather indices, which predict the likelihood and severity of wildfires. Sub-seasonal predictions cover a period of about two to eight weeks, while seasonal predictions cover a period of several months to a year.

Earth observation in Response

Warning and alert activities flow directly from on-going preparedness. When a risk area is monitored on a regular basis, it is usually possible to determine that an event may be imminent, requiring different observation periods and the generation of information specifically tied to the predicted event.

In the immediate aftermath of a wildfire, the primary issue is timeliness. Satellites can provide rapid situational awareness over a large area, typically on a daily basis.

Please find below some illustrative examples of distinguished EO services that can provide assistance during the occurrence of a fire.:

- 1) Spatiotemporal fire-spread information, through dynamic modelling by simulating evolving fire, through different simulators and Numerical Weather Prediction models. EO can be used to capture high-resolution images of fires from space, which can be used to track the location and size of the fire over time as well as sensors on aircraft, drones, or other platforms can be used to collect data about the fire, such as temperature, smoke density.
- 2) Risk assessment and evacuation plans considering vulnerability, exposure and critical infrastructure. It is important to have evacuation plans in place before a wildfire occurs, practice them regularly so that everyone knows what to do and use them appropriately in the event of an emergency.
- 3) 24/7 active fire detection service for effectively monitoring forest fires in near-real time. These services can also be connected to a central monitoring system that can send out alerts and initiate response procedures in the event of a fire.

Investing in the response phase is key. In Europe, the European Commission has established Emergency Management Services to address the integration of satellite data for emergencies and is currently collaborating with the International Charter to provide Value Adding services to support the exploitation of

imagery supplied via the Charter to European organisations for response in areas pertinent to the policy sectors of Europe, primarily in its territories and in regions where humanitarian assistance is invoked.

Earth observation in **Recovery**

The recovery phase of wildfire management refers to the efforts taken to restore and rebuild impacted communities and ecosystems after a wildfire has occurred. The recovery phase of wildfire management is a complex and multifaceted process that requires the coordination of multiple stakeholders and the allocation of resources to address the various impacts of the wildfire. Satellite EO can offer cost savings in monitoring of large areas or especially complex disasters where large number of organisations are present in the field and where recovery operations remain in place for several years.

Examples of EO services in the recovery phase of WFRM can be:

- 1) Fast-track hazard assessment maps for cascading events such as soil erosion, floods and landslide that include information on the location and intensity of hazards, as well as the potential impacts on people, infrastructure, and the environment. Fast-track hazard assessment maps can be used by emergency responders, government agencies, and other stakeholders to identify the most critical areas and resources to protect in the event of a cascading event.
- 2) Identification of critical points, regarding providing emergency assistance to those who have been mostly affected as well as rehabilitating mostly-impacted ecosystems.
- 3) Proposal of short-term mitigation measures, such as implementing fire-safe land management practices, including cleaning up dry leaves and debris, mowing grass, and maintaining a buffer zone around structures; as well as long-term measures, e.g. implementing land use planning policies that consider wildfire risk

Conclusion & suggested points for discussion in WG exchange

Considering the several ways that Earth Observation can be used to relate with wildfires, all Working Groups have to take into consideration the important contribution of EO. This information can be used to improve wildfire management and planning, and to reduce the negative impacts of these fires on people and ecosystems. Due to the increasing future wildfire risk, wildfire community will have to embrace Earth Observation through the disaster risk management cycle: **Prevention**, **Mitigation** and **Preparedness**; **Response** and **Recovery**, adopting effective strategies to mitigate risk.

Table 1: Earth Observation discussion topics proposed for WG exchange

	Topic 1 (Prevention and preparedness)	Topic 2 (Response)	Topic 3 (Recovery)
Environmental & Ecology WG	Policy-making: By employing EO methodologies to examine previous occurrences, understand wildfires' causes and consequences on environment and inform strategies for mitigating their negative impacts.	Monitoring: Cost-efficient manner to monitor real time and near-real time wildfires' location, size, and intensity and impacts on the environment.	Recovery: Monitor the regrowth of vegetation and the return of wildlife

Societal WG	Policy-making: Inform the development of policies and programs aimed at mitigating the impact of wildfires on society, by comprehending the underlying factors and repercussions of wildfires.	Societal awareness: In case of emergency, provide EO outputs and information through social media, news, and other channels.	Impact assessment and Community support: Identify post-wildfire threats to human life and safety, property, and critical resources as well as provide delineation of priority zones for restoration purposes.
Infrastructure WG	Planning; design and impact assessment: 1) detailed maps of high-risk areas to identify suitable locations for infrastructure projects; 2) assess the potential environmental impacts of infrastructure projects, including the effects on WFRM.	Maintenance and monitoring: monitor affected infrastructure and identify any potential issues in order to plan immediate repairs and reconstruction efforts, as well as to identify vulnerabilities in the infrastructure network.	Disaster management: In the event of a wildfire, assess the location and extent of the wildfire, the damage to infrastructure and plan for recovery and reconstruction efforts.
Insurance WG	Insurance products and pricing: EO to inform for high-risk areas to charge higher premiums for coverage or to develop insurance products specifically tailored to cover wildfire risk.	Quick estimate of what is burnt: Assist the parametric insurance: if a certain parameter threshold is reached in a specific location	Damage assessment: used by insurance companies helping to determine the extent of coverage that is required and to speed up the claims process
Civil Protection WG	Risk assessment: Assess the risk of wildfires in a given area and prepare for an imminent disaster.	Monitoring: assist the deployment of resources and the evacuation of people and livestock, through modelling and simulating the monitoring the spread of a wildfire in real-time.	Damage assessment: assisting authorities to prioritize their response efforts and to identify areas that may require additional support.

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4. Conclusion & next steps

As a socio-natural phenomenon, wildfire risk emerges at the dynamic intersection between hazards, exposure and vulnerability, determined by a range of socioeconomic and climatic drivers. In Europe, unmanaged fuel-intensive landscapes have been expanding rapidly on abandoned agricultural and pasture lands, constituting a major driver for increasing wildfire hazard over the past decades. Also, climate change affects fuel moisture, increasing the weather-driven danger of forest fires and pushing areas of moderate fire danger north, covering central Europe (de Rigo et al., 2017). At the same time, expanding wildland-urban interfaces and poor land planning ignoring wildfire risk, have increased exposure of human lives, private property and economic activity. As a third component of wildfire risk, vulnerability is situation and context dependent, determined by individual characteristics and their complex interactions. As a result of different degrees of vulnerability, damages and losses differ across individuals, indicating a complex interdependency between the severity of a wildfire event and the impacts it causes to the affected community.

In light of this complexity and an increase in the magnitude and severity of fires, current European WFRM are challenged (Rego et al., 2018), and more effective and integrated solutions are called for. Acknowledging wildfires as a complex risk, characterised by the interconnection and dynamics within the socioeconomic system, Firelogue aims to connect the European WFRM community to identify related conflicting and synergistic interests and co-create holistic and innovative WFRM strategies, that are effective in reducing wildfire risk and perceived as just by affected communities.

This deliverable aims to inform future WG exchange formats of Firelogue, building on evidence from existing wildfire risk and WFRM research, as well as TS expertise. As a first collection and synthesis of current practices in WFRM and possible discussion topics structured against the 4 TS, this interim version of D1.4 starts to set out a knowledge base for dialogue workshops, which is continuously updated with insights from WG discussions and IA and FireEURisk innovations.

As the planning of workshop cycle I substantiates in course of the first quarter in 2023 and workshop participants are confirmed, a close interaction between the Socioeconomic and Climate Change TS and WGs will inform the identification of discussion topics and relevant policy aspects in WFRM. This will feed back into and refine the TS factsheets, to serve as a basis for thematic input into cross-WG exchange, following the first round of WG discussions. This procedure is then repeated towards the end of the second project year for the second workshop cycle, focusing on the TS Technology and Earth Observation. Moreover, ongoing work in WP1 will continuously contribute to the knowledge collection conducted in this task. Insights and lessons learned from past wildfire events are analyzed through a review of existing peer-reviewed and grey literature in Task 1.2. Innovations from IAs and FireEURisk are collected by Task 1.3 by means of a harmonized template, assessing the maturity level of newly developed technologies in WFRM. Thus, we aim to establish a comprehensive collection of novel and past WFRM practices, serving as an extensive knowledge base for the informed design of effective and inclusive future wildfire management across Europe.

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